

Article

Portfolio optimization under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis. Empirical evidence of the dependence between optimal portfolio structure and ESG Risk Scores

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Abstract: *This paper aims to perform a portfolio optimization under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis and measures whether there is dependence between the optimal portfolio structures thus obtained and ESG Risk Scores. The investigation of such an issue may be justified by the fact that ESG reporting is intended to become a stable evolutionary strategy (in the sense of Smith & Price), and portfolio optimization under such a behavioral hypothesis is in line with behavioral finances, where investors are considered to be twice as sensitive to losses as to gains (in the sense of Kahneman & Tversky). Following such an approach expressed methodologically and empirically, the result we reach, on the data we analyzed, is that: optimal portfolio structures are dependent on ESG Risk Scores and even if this statistical dependence is considered to be of low intensity we observe a pattern. The dependence is in the opposite direction up to the portfolio tangent to the Sharpe Efficient Frontier (the portfolio with the maximum Sortino ratio), after which, the dependence is in the same direction. We also observe other patterns in the analysis.*

Keywords: *Portfolio investment decision; Risk analysis; Mean-Semivariance Behavior Hypothesis; ESG Risk Score.*

1. Introduction

Financial portfolio optimization within the sustainability paradigm has also become an important concern among finance researchers. This paradigm offers researchers a number of new avenues of research, given the institutionally created regulatory tools for realizing sustainable processes in human society (in our view, sustainability is the finality of a process - example of finality in biology: survival - and sustainability is a property of a process - example of property in mathematics: continuity of a function).

One normative institutional tool found in the sustainability paradigm is ESG (Environment, Social and Governance) reporting by companies. Even though this tool for measuring the economic process at the firm level is not yet a mandatory reporting standard, many capital market investors refer to it when choosing their investments in shares of listed companies. This fact is very well argued recently by Pedersen et al. (2021) in a paper that we can consider relevant to finance, and on the specifics of our study we find arguments in Zhang et al. (2023).

What we aim in this paper is to formally and empirically describe the optimization of the equity portfolio under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis (MSBH) and to investigate whether there is a statistically observed dependence between the optimal structure of such a portfolio and the ESG Risk Scores. In this sense, after describing the formal research framework, our empirical study will be conducted on stocks issued by companies listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange (BVB) and for which

there are reports, for the year 2023, on ESG Risk Score by Sustainalytics (we can consider this portfolio as the ESG portfolio of the BVB for the year 2023).

The choice for such a study can be justified in addition to those mentioned above by the fact that more and more companies are opting for such reporting, which will imply in the future, we say, a Stable Evolution Strategy (ESS) in the sense of Smith & Price (1973).

Briefly, our work is structured along the following research directions: a first research direction refers to the realization of a methodological framework that provides some analytical solutions for portfolio optimization under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis; the second research direction will refer to the application of these analytical solutions and the obtaining of empirical results; the third research direction is to measure whether the optimal portfolios obtained by us under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis and located on the Markowitz Efficient Frontier are correlated with the ESG Risk Scores of the portfolio companies.

2. Literature review

The issue of portfolio optimization under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis is topical and increasingly debated in the literature, especially in recent years, after the 2007 financial crisis and the COVID 19 pandemic. This behavioral hypothesis is not new, it was even considered by Markowitz (1959) who presents in a whole chapter (Chapter IX) formal aspects of this possibility, as opposed to the Mean-Variance Behavioral Hypothesis found in Markowitz (1952) on which Modern Portfolio Theory was built.

Even though the mean-variance criterion is the most accepted criterion by academics and the financial industry for portfolio optimization due to its simplicity in performing the optimization, the mean-semivariance criterion is arguably more relevant from a behavioral and portfolio performance measurement perspective. Some of the recent evidence in this regard is adduced by Wang & Yan (2021), and more skeptical evidence is provided by Grootveld & Hallerbach (1999).

The Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis is that, unlike the Mean-Variance Behavioral Hypothesis, where the measure of risk is given by variance, for this case the measure of risk is given by semivariance. In fact, the consideration of this hypothesis has opened a new avenue of research in portfolio optimization, which is also known as Post-Modern Portfolio Theory. In this acceptance, the theory uses the concept of downside risk of return since it is believed that investors are not interested in considering the standard deviation of returns to measure their risk, but are interested in the downside risk, which is measured by semideviation. One argument for this would be the consistency of this hypothesis with research that has been done in behavioral economics, where Kahneman and Tversky (1979) tell us that people are twice as sensitive to losses as to gains. Which makes sense of such an approach.

Following a review of the literature, we find that, even though the issue of mean-squared is quite old in the portfolio optimization research space (Markowitz, 1959), Post-Modern Portfolio Theory was first highlighted by Rom and Ferguson (1993), two software engineers. A year later, Sortino and Price (1994) propose within this theory an indicator to measure the excess of the investor's expected return over a target return (considered in practice to be the risk-free rate) per unit of downside risk. This indicator is similar to the Sharpe ratio (Sharpe, 1966) used to measure performance in Modern Portfolio Theory.

More recently, some of the contributions on downside risk that we may find useful for financial theory and practice are the contributions of Estrada (2002), Estrada (2004), Estrada (2006), Estrada (2007), Estrada (2008) and the remark of Venkataraman (2021). Recent evidence on the use of downside systematic risk by investors in determining expected returns can be found in Markowski (2024). Alternatives on the measure of downside risk from an econometric perspective (VaR, CVaR, EVaR) can be found in Palomar (2024).

3. Methodology

In the following, we present the methodology we use.

We define the following continuous random variables, defined as: $r_i \sim N(\bar{r}_i, \sigma_i^2)$ and $r_m \sim N(\bar{r}_m, \sigma_m^2)$ and construct a special portfolio (P), comprising a part (α) financial security i ($i \in M$), and part $(1 - \alpha)$ market portfolio (M).

where: r_i = return on financial security i ; r_m = the stock market return calculated on the representative stock market index; $r_i = \ln \frac{P_{i(t)}}{P_{i(t-1)}}$, $P_{i(t)}$ = the price of security i at time t , and $P_{i(t-1)}$ = the price of security i at time $t-1$; $r_m = \ln \frac{I(t)}{I(t-1)}$, $I(t)$ = the value of the representative stock index at time t , and $I(t-1)$ = the value of the representative stock index at time $t-1$

Given the above, on the mean-variance criterion, the equations of this portfolio can be written as follows (Sharpe, 1964):

$$E(P) = \alpha E(r_i) + (1 - \alpha)E(r_m) \tag{1}$$

$$\sigma(P) = \sqrt{\alpha^2 \sigma_i^2 + (1 - \alpha)^2 \sigma_m^2 + 2\alpha(1 - \alpha)\sigma_{im}} \tag{2}$$

$$\alpha + (1 - \alpha) = 1 \tag{3}$$

where: $E(P)$ = portfolio return expectation; $\sigma(P)$ = portfolio return volatility P; σ_{im} = covariance between return on security i and stock market return; σ_i^2 = variance of the return on security i ; σ_m^2 = variance of stock market return

If the investor is characterized by the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis, we write equation (2) heuristically as follows:

$$\sigma(P)_{down} \approx \sqrt{\alpha^2 \sigma_{i(down)}^2 + (1 - \alpha)^2 \sigma_{m(down)}^2 + 2\alpha(1 - \alpha)\sigma_{im(down)}} \tag{4}$$

where: $\sigma_{i(down)}^2$ = downside variance of returns for title i ; $\sigma_{m(down)}^2$ = downside variance of return for market; $\sigma_{im(down)}$ downside covariance between tilte and market; $\sigma(P)_{down}$ = downside risk of portfolio (P)

In agreement with Estrada (2006, 2007), we write the analytic solutions for the above variables as follows: $\sigma_{im(down)} = E\{\min[(r_i - \bar{r}_i), 0] \cdot \min[(r_m - \bar{r}_m), 0]\}$; $\sigma_{i(down)}^2 = E\{\min[(r_i - \bar{r}_i), 0]^2\}$; $\sigma_{m(down)}^2 = E\{\min[(r_m - \bar{r}_m), 0]^2\}$

What we are now interested in is to calculate the contribution of security i to the formation of downside systematic risk, i.e. we will look for how portfolio P behaves on the return-downside risk criterion in the neighborhood of the M coordinate point $(\sigma_{m(down)}, E(r_m))$ on the Sharpe Efficient Frontier (CML), which, given that we are considering the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis, we will call the Downside Capital Market Line (D-CML). In this sense, the slope of the CML $\left(\frac{E(r_m) - rf}{\sigma_m}\right)$ becomes the D-CML slope $\left(\frac{E(r_m) - rf}{\sigma_{m(down)}}\right)$, where rf = risk free rate.

Formally we will have:

$$\frac{dE(P)}{d\sigma(P)_{down}} = \frac{dE(P)}{d\alpha} \cdot \frac{d\alpha}{d\sigma(P)_{down}} = \frac{\frac{dE(P)}{d\alpha}}{\frac{d\sigma(P)_{down}}{d\alpha}} \tag{5}$$

For the numerator of the last expression in equation (5) we have:

$$\frac{d}{d\alpha} \alpha E(r_i) + \frac{d}{d\alpha} (1 - \alpha)E(r_m) = E(r_i) - E(r_m) \tag{6}$$

For the denominator of the last expression in equation (5) we have:

$$\left. \frac{d}{d\alpha} \sqrt{\alpha^2 \sigma_{i(down)}^2 + (1 - \alpha)^2 \sigma_{m(down)}^2 + 2\alpha(1 - \alpha)\sigma_{im(down)}} \right\} \Rightarrow \frac{d\sigma(P)_{down}}{du} \cdot \frac{du}{d\alpha} \quad (7)$$

we note with $\sigma(P)_{down} = \sqrt{u}$

$$\frac{d\sigma(P)_{down}}{du} \cdot \frac{du}{d\alpha} = \frac{\alpha(\sigma_{i(down)}^2 + \sigma_{m(down)}^2 - 2\sigma_{im(down)}) + \sigma_{im(down)} - \sigma_{m(down)}^2}{\sigma(P)_{down}} \quad (8)$$

From (5), (6) and (8), by substitution, we have:

$$\frac{dE(P)}{d\sigma(P)_{down}} = \frac{[E(r_i) - E(r_m)] \cdot \sigma(P)_{down}}{\alpha(\sigma_{i(down)}^2 + \sigma_{m(down)}^2 - 2\sigma_{im(down)}) + \sigma_{im(down)} - \sigma_{m(down)}^2} \quad (9)$$

But in the vicinity of the point M ($\sigma_{m(down)}, E(r_m)$), we have:

$$\alpha = 0 \rightarrow \sigma(P)_{down} = \sigma_{m(down)}$$

As a result, we will have:

$$\frac{dE(P)}{d\sigma(P)_{down}} = \frac{[E(r_i) - E(r_m)] \cdot \sigma_{m(down)}}{\sigma_{im(down)} - \sigma_{m(down)}^2} \quad (10)$$

Considering now on the mean-semivariance criterion that the slope $\frac{dE(P)}{d\sigma(P)_{down}}$ at point M is the slope D-CML, we write:

$$\frac{[E(r_i) - E(r_m)] \cdot \sigma_{m(down)}}{\sigma_{im(down)} - \sigma_{m(down)}^2} = \frac{E(r_m) - rf}{\sigma_{m(down)}} \quad (11)$$

Therefore, equation (11) gives:

$$E(r_i) = rf + [E(r_m) - rf] \cdot \frac{\sigma_{im(down)}}{\sigma_{m(down)}^2} \quad (12)$$

where: $[E(r_m) - rf]$ = market risk premium; $[E(r_m) - rf] \cdot \frac{\sigma_{im(down)}}{\sigma_{m(down)}^2}$ = risk premium of security i ;

$\frac{\sigma_{im(down)}}{\sigma_{m(down)}^2}$ = downside systematic risk.

Equation (12) is in agreement with Estrada (2007), D-CAPM (Downside Capital Assets Price Model).

Downside systematic risk can be written like this:

$$\frac{E\left[\frac{(r_i - \bar{r}_i) - |r_i - \bar{r}_i|}{2} \cdot \frac{(r_m - \bar{r}_m) - |r_m - \bar{r}_m|}{2}\right]}{E\left[\frac{(r_m - \bar{r}_m) - |r_m - \bar{r}_m|}{2}\right]^2} \quad (13)$$

Now, if the investor determines the expected return of the stocks in his portfolio based on a normative model of the form above and we accept that the downside risk for a portfolio of stocks ($\sigma_{p(down)}$) can be written heuristically as follows (see Estrada, 2008):

$$\sigma_{p(down)} \approx \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij}(down)} \quad (14)$$

then the portfolio structure with minimum semivariance and the efficient portfolio structure under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis can be analytically determined as follows:

- for the case of the portfolio with minimum semivariance under the mean-semivariance behavioral assumption:

Let be the following Lagrange function (L) for minimizing the portfolio semivariance:

$$L = \min \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij}(down) + \lambda_1 (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1) \right\} \rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{\partial L}{\partial x_i} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda_1} = 0 \end{cases} \rightarrow \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n x_j \sigma_{ij}(down) + \lambda_1 = 0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 1 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where: x_i = weight of security i in the portfolio; x_j = weight of security j in the portfolio; $\sigma_{ij(down)} = E\{\min[(r_i - B), 0] \cdot \min[(r_j - B), 0]\}$, B = benchmark

We define B :

$$B = \max(\bar{r}_i, rf) = \frac{\bar{r}_i + rf + |\bar{r}_i - rf|}{2} \tag{16}$$

The two systems in relation (15) are equivalent:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial L}{\partial x_i} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[1/2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[1/2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} \right] + \lambda_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) = \\ &= \left[1/2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)}) \right] + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (1) \right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)}) + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i) - 0 \right) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} + \lambda_1 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda_1} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} \left[1/2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} \left[1/2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} \left[\lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \end{aligned}$$

Further, by solving the system in relation (15) matrixally, we can write sequentially:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11(down)} & \sigma_{12(down)} & \cdots & \sigma_{1n(down)} & 1 \\ \sigma_{21(down)} & \sigma_{22(down)} & \cdots & \sigma_{2n(down)} & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{n1(down)} & \sigma_{n2(down)} & \cdots & \sigma_{nn(down)} & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11(down)} & \sigma_{12(down)} & \cdots & \sigma_{1n(down)} & 1 \\ \sigma_{21(down)} & \sigma_{22(down)} & \cdots & \sigma_{2n(down)} & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{n1(down)} & \sigma_{n2(down)} & \cdots & \sigma_{nn(down)} & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{18}$$

Given the portfolio structure obtained from equation (18), the expected portfolio return $[E(rp)]$ is:

$$E(rp) = (x_1 x_2 \dots x_n) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} E(r_1) \\ E(r_2) \\ \vdots \\ E(r_n) \end{pmatrix} \tag{19}$$

and downside risk for the portfolio with minimum semi-variance $[\sigma_{rp(down)}^\Omega]$ is:

$$\sigma_{p(down)}^\Omega = \sqrt{(x_1 x_2 \dots x_n) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11(down)} & \sigma_{12(down)} & \dots & \sigma_{1n(down)} \\ \sigma_{21(down)} & \sigma_{22(down)} & \dots & \sigma_{2n(down)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{n1(down)} & \sigma_{n2(down)} & \dots & \sigma_{nn(down)} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix}} \tag{20}$$

- for the efficient portfolio case under the mean-semivariance behavioral assumption:

Let be the following Lagrange function (L) for minimizing the portfolio semivariance with the investor's target return $[E(rp_\Theta)]$:

$$L = \min \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_\Theta) \right) + \lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right\}$$

$$\rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{\partial L}{\partial x_i} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda_1} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda_2} = 0 \end{cases} \rightarrow \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} + \lambda_1 E(r_i) + \lambda_2 = 0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) = E(rp_\Theta) \\ \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 1 \end{cases} \tag{21}$$

The two systems in relation (21) are equivalent:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial L}{\partial x_i} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_\Theta) \right) + \lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_\Theta) \right) \right] + \\ &\quad + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)}) + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i E(r_i)) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} E(rp_\Theta) \right) + \lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (1) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)}) + \lambda_1 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (x_i E(r_i)) - 0 \right) + \lambda_2 (1 - 0) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n x_j \sigma_{ij} + \lambda_1 E(r_i) + \lambda_2 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda_1} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_\Theta) \right) + \lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(down)} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} \left[\lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_\Theta) \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_1} \left[\lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_{\Theta}) \\
 \frac{\partial L}{\partial \lambda_2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(\text{down})} + \lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_{\Theta}) \right) + \lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\
 &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n x_i x_j \sigma_{ij(\text{down})} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_2} \left[\lambda_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i E(r_i) - E(rp_{\Theta}) \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_2} \left[\lambda_2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1 \right) \right] = \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^n x_i - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

Next, by solving the system (21) matrixally, we can write sequentially:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11(\text{down})} & \cdots & \sigma_{1n(\text{down})} & E(r_1) & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{n1(\text{down})} & \cdots & \sigma_{nn(\text{down})} & E(r_n) & 1 \\ E(r_1) & \cdots & E(r_n) & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \cdots & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \\ \lambda_1 \\ \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ E(rp_{\Theta}) \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{22}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \\ \lambda_1 \\ \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11(\text{down})} & \cdots & \sigma_{1n(\text{down})} & E(r_1) & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{n1(\text{down})} & \cdots & \sigma_{nn(\text{down})} & E(r_n) & 1 \\ E(r_1) & \cdots & E(r_n) & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \cdots & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ E(rp_{\Theta}) \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{23}$$

and downside risk for the efficient portfolio $[\sigma_{rp(\text{down})}^{\Psi}]$ is:

$$\sigma_{p(\text{down})}^{\Psi} = \sqrt{(x_1 \ x_2 \ \dots \ x_n) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11(\text{down})} & \sigma_{12(\text{down})} & \cdots & \sigma_{1n(\text{down})} \\ \sigma_{12(\text{down})} & \sigma_{22(\text{down})} & \cdots & \sigma_{2n(\text{down})} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sigma_{n1(\text{down})} & \sigma_{n2(\text{down})} & \cdots & \sigma_{nn(\text{down})} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix}} \tag{24}$$

Having said that, after determining the structure of the efficient portfolios located on the Markowitz Efficient Frontier, based on the above, we determine, using the correlation coefficient, whether there is dependence between these optimal structures and the ESG Risk Scores of the analyzed companies.

4. Data

The data used in this study are the daily closing share prices of companies listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange (BVB) and for which ESG Risk Scores have been calculated in 2023. The companies listed and for which ESG Risk Scores were calculated by Sustainalytics for the year 2023 were 10 (see Table 1). The ESG risk ratings given by Sustainalytics are categorized as follows: negligible (0-10); low (10-20); medium (20-30); high (30-40); severe (>40). Data on companies' ESG risks were obtained from the BVB website and summarized by us in Table 1. The analysis period of closing stock prices is one stock market year, 252 days (27. 12. 2022 - 29. 12. 2023). The daily closing stock prices for the 10 companies and the daily values of the BET stock index (considered as the representative index of the stock market) were obtained from Refinitiv Eikon. The risk-free rate in our calculations is Romania 5 Years bond Yield, as of 12/29/2023, obtained from the National Bank of Romania (BNR) website.

Table 1. ESG Risk Scores of Companies (Sustainalytics, 2023)

Companies/ Information	Date of the ESG Risk Score	The type of report	ESG Risk Score	ESG Risk Ranking Score
Antibiotics	04.12.2023	Core Framework	22,2	28/443 top 7%
BRD	02.11.2023	Core Framework	14,4	28/492 top 6%

OMV Petrom	28.11.2023	Core Framework	24,6	3/61 top 4%
Rompetrol Well Services	21.11.2023	Core Framework	16,9	6/85 top 7%
SNGN Romgaz	09.11.2023	Core Framework	29	15/16 top 9%
Aquila	13.04.2023	Core Framework	22,4	51/95 top 54%
One United Properties	20.11.2023	Core Framework	18,4	92/284 top 33%
TeraPlast	07/12/2023	Core Framework	23,4	51/159 top 32%
SNTGN Transgaz	20/12/2023	Core Framework	27,6	33/117 top 28%
Transport Trade Services	28.11.2023	Core Framework	21,8	36/103 top 35%

Source: Bucharest Stock Exchange (own processing)

5. Results

Given the above methodological framework, in the following we will present the empirical results that we have obtained after applying it on the above data.

In this section, we present our results on the optimal portfolios obtained under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis and highlight some issues that we find relevant.

First, Table 2 presents the results for 15 portfolios, including the capital market portfolio (M), for expected return, downside risk, D-CML and Sortino ratio.

In the following, we would like to clarify the results of the analysis:

- portfolios in the range (p (1), p (5)) are inefficient portfolios (for the same downside risk we have portfolios with higher returns);
- portfolios in the range [p (5), p (14)] are optimal portfolios on the Markowitz Efficient Frontier;
- portfolio p (5) is the portfolio with minimum downside risk (characteristic of extremely risk-averse investors); this portfolio offers investors the lowest downside risk (9,76%) and a return of 20,26%;
- portfolio p (11) is the portfolio tangent to the Sharpe Efficient Frontier and it offers the highest return above the risk free rate per unit of downside risk; this portfolio has the highest Sortino ratio and is characteristic of risk averse investors;
- portfolios in the range (p (11), p (14)] are characteristic of risk-averse investors;
- as we can see from the data, no portfolio has a Sortino ratio higher than the Sortino ratio of the equity market portfolio (M); at a portfolio return equal to the market return (portfolio [p (9)]), the downside risk of this portfolio is higher than the downside risk of the market portfolio.

Table 2. Capital market portfolio, inefficient portfolios, efficient portfolios

Optimal portfolio/ Indicators	Downside risk (year)	Return portfolio (year)	Sortino ratio
M	8,64%	23,34%	2,00
p (1)	11,49%	14,00%	0,69
p (2)	10,59%	16,00%	0,94
p (3)	10,00%	18,00%	1,19
p (4)	9,83%	19,00%	1,32
p (5)	9,76%	20,26%	1,46
p (6)	9,78%	21,00%	1,53
p (7)	9,90%	22,00%	1,61
p (8)	10,11%	23,00%	1,68
p (9)	10,20%	23,34%	1,69
p (10)	10,41%	24,00%	1,72

p (11)	11,75%	27,00%	1,78
p (12)	13,58%	30,00%	1,76
p (13)	17,31%	35,00%	1,67
p (14)	21,50%	40,00%	1,58

Source: Author own calculation

Synoptically, our results can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Markowitz and Sharpe Efficient Frontiers under the Mean-Semivariance Behavioral Hypothesis

Source: Author own calculation

Second, we perform the following further analysis of the previously obtained results on synthetic indicators such as: growth rate of the optimal portfolio return; growth rate of the optimal portfolio downside risk; marginal cost of downside risk as a function of portfolio return; downside risk elasticity of the portfolio to portfolio return. Following this analysis we obtained the following results:

- the growth rate of portfolio return is higher than the growth rate of downside risk until portfolio p (11), the portfolio with the maximum Sortino ratio, after which these rates are reversed, the growth rate of downside risk exceeds the growth rate of portfolio return (see Figure 2);
- the marginal cost of downside risk is increasing, but for all the cases analyzed, the change in downside risk is less than the change in portfolio return (see Figure 3);
- the evolution of the downside risk elasticity with respect to the portfolio return is subunitary for the optimal portfolios in the interval [p (5), p (11)], for the portfolio p (11) we have unit elasticity, and for the interval (p (11), p (14)] we observe supraunitary elasticity (see Figure 4).

Figure 2. Evolutions of growth rate of return and downside risk

Source: Author own calculation

Figure 3. Evolution of marginal downside risk

Source: Author own calculation

Figure 4. Evolution of Downside risk elasticity

Source: Author own calculation

Third, relevant results also relate to the optimal portfolio structures located on the Markowitz Efficient Frontier. As can be seen from Table 3, among these are portfolios in which some stocks are short sold, considering that this is possible.

Table 3. Efficient portfolio structures

Companies/ Optimal structures of the portfolios	p (5)	p (6)	p (7)	p (8)	p (9)	p (10)	p (11)	p (12)	p (13)	p (14)
Antibiotice	3%	3%	3%	2%	2%	2%	1%	0%	-2%	-3%
BRD	3%	6%	10%	13%	15%	17%	29%	40%	60%	79%
OMV	12%	14%	16%	19%	20%	21%	29%	37%	50%	62%
Rompetrol Well	13%	11%	9%	7%	6%	5%	-2%	-8%	-19%	-30%
Romgaz	12%	13%	14%	15%	16%	17%	21%	25%	32%	39%
AQUILA	20%	18%	16%	14%	13%	12%	5%	-1%	-11%	-22%
ONE United	43%	39%	34%	29%	27%	24%	8%	-7%	-32%	-58%
Teraplast	-4%	-4%	-4%	-3%	-3%	-3%	-2%	-1%	1%	3%
Transgaz	1%	1%	3%	4%	4%	5%	9%	12%	18%	24%
Transport Trade	-1%	-1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	2%	4%	5%

Source: Author own calculation

Fourth we conclude with our results representing the statistical dependence between optimal portfolio structure and ESG Risk Score. Following this analysis we obtained the following results (see Figure 5):

- optimal portfolios between [p (5), p (11)] are inversely correlated with ESG Risk Scores;
- optimal portfolios between [p (11), p (14)] are correlated in the same sense with ESG Risk Scores.

Figure 5. Evolution of correlations between optimal portfolio structures and ESG Risk Score

Source: Author own calculation

6. Conclusions

Given the above results, we summarize with the following conclusions:

- the portfolios in the range [p (5), p (14)] are optimal portfolios located on the Markowitz Efficient Frontier and dominated by the Sharpe Efficient Frontier;
- portfolio p (5) is the portfolio with minimal downside risk (characteristic of extremely risk-averse investors); this portfolio offers investors the lowest downside risk (9.76%) and a return of 20.26%;
- portfolio p (11) is the portfolio on the Markowitz Efficient Frontier and tangent to the Sharpe Efficient Frontier; it offers the highest return above the risk-free rate per unit of downside risk (maximum Sortino ratio);
- the marginal cost of downside risk is increasing, but this rate of change is sub unit (for a one unit increase in profitability, downside risk increases by less than one unit);
- the downside risk is inelastic and increasing for efficient portfolios in the range [p (5), p (11)) (one percent increase in portfolio returns → an increase by less than one percent of the downside risk); for the portfolio p (11) we have unit elasticity, and after this portfolio we have supra unit elasticity;
- efficient portfolio structures are dependent on ESG Risk Scores and even if this dependence is of low intensity, what is noteworthy is that, on the Markowitz Efficient Frontier, those between [p (5), p (11)) are inversely correlated with ESG Risk Scores (high ESG Risk Score → weight of the security in the portfolio is lower) and those between [p (11), p (14)] are correlated in the same direction.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Data availability

<https://eikon.refinitiv.com/>

<https://bvbresearch.ro/ReportDashboard/ESGScores>

[https://www.bnr.ro/Titluri-de-stat---rate-de-referinta-\(fixing\)-6332.aspx#](https://www.bnr.ro/Titluri-de-stat---rate-de-referinta-(fixing)-6332.aspx#)

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